

DataMap

PARSEC PROJECT

Dataset Management Planning Tool

Group involved:

Wellington Queiroz (Tony)

Ricardo, André, Caio, Rosa, Wesley, Felipe e Márcio

Data Science and Big Data Researcher at POLI-USP

Why use a tool to manage datasets?

- PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook
 - <https://zenodo.org/record/3891427#.YUurmyZv9Gp>
- Current way of organizing and managing the datasets: Excel workbook
 - https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fVC_IU35tMZ1ZNpRz0p

Variable name	Variable description provided	Variable type	Entry	Quality
Number_of_publications	A numeric count of the number of publications per country	number	numeric	medium
Country_code	A 3-letter code representing the country	string	string	high
Year	The year of publication	number	numeric	high
Abstract_text	The abstract text of the publication	string	text	medium
Keywords	Keywords associated with the publication	string	text	medium
Journal_title	The title of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_volume	The volume number of the journal	number	numeric	medium
Journal_issue	The issue number of the journal	number	numeric	medium
Journal_page	The page number of the journal	number	numeric	medium
Journal_year	The year of publication	number	numeric	medium
Journal_publisher	The publisher of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn	The ISSN of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_eissn	The E-ISSN of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_pissn	The P-ISSN of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_l	The ISSN-L of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_o	The ISSN-O of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_x	The ISSN-X of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_z	The ISSN-Z of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_w	The ISSN-W of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_y	The ISSN-Y of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_v	The ISSN-V of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_u	The ISSN-U of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_t	The ISSN-T of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_s	The ISSN-S of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_r	The ISSN-R of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_q	The ISSN-Q of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_p	The ISSN-P of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_o	The ISSN-O of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_n	The ISSN-N of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_m	The ISSN-M of the journal	string	text	medium
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Journal_issn_h	The ISSN-H of the journal	string	text	medium
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Journal_issn_f	The ISSN-F of the journal	string	text	medium
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Journal_issn_d	The ISSN-D of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_c	The ISSN-C of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_b	The ISSN-B of the journal	string	text	medium
Journal_issn_a	The ISSN-A of the journal	string	text	medium

Is this really necessary?

In order to ensure compliance with policies and procedures described in the PARSEC [DDOMP](#) document so as the community standards and best practices, a tool that could **automate**, organize and **manage** the **datasets**, attributes, **metadata** and rules (especially with a huge amount of data) it would be helpful and welcome. Not to mention that it would significantly increase efficiency and productivity as well as reduce the chances of human error when dealing with spreadsheets manually.

In addition to these main reasons, we have other features in using a tool to manage datasets such as API Integrations, privacy & security, multilingual support that could help to avoid communication noise in terms of definitions (eg: synonyms with different semantics), user friendly interface and better user experience.

Figure 1: The Synthesis Centre data lifecycle (from Specht 2017).

SIMPLE ARCHITECTURE MAP

PARSEC

SIMPLE AND GENERIC VIEW OF DATAMAP STACK

DATAMAP Isn't just a single tool but a platform which hosts tools. So, the Data Dictionary is a tool hosted by datamap.

Catalog of Google DataSet Search

Google Data Search

<https://toolbox.google.com/datasetsearch>

Natasha Noy and Matthew Burgess and Dan Brickley , Google Dataset Search: Building a search engine for datasets in an open Web ecosystem, WebConf 2019. available at: <https://ai.google/research/pubs/pub47845>

— Towards to the Metadata Catalog

Properties of the Google Search (Mandatories and desirable):

Reference:

- Towards to the Data Set Metadata

<https://developers.google.com/search/docs/data-types/dataset>

- Vocabulary: [Schema.org](https://schema.org)
- DataSet: schema.org > Dataset

BASIC TOP LEVEL VIEW

APPLICATION DIAGRAM

PARSEC PROJECT | DataMap - Application Diagram [top-level]

versão: 0.31
data: 03052021
autor: TEAM POLI USP

UML CLASS DIAGRAM

NEW FEATURES - a working in progress...

- **SSO (Single Sign On) and OAuth client:** Provides applications the ability for “secure designated access.” The users will be able to login (or consuming the api) using his account/credentials. **E.g:** ORCID, OSF account.
- **OAuth Server:** Datamap will handle an oauth server service, so an third party application consuming the api/backend can use the datamap account/credentials to authorize and log in. **E.g:** webapp, mobileapp, third party app or different frontends.
- **PreProcessing DataSet:** When creating/registering a new dataset file, the data analysis module will preprocess the file and automatically read, interpret, create and populate all attributes, then save the data in the data dictionary module and generate a basic summary of the dataset (records, statics etc).
- **Spatial Data Science (SDS):** When the file/dataset contains spatial references like location, distance etc, the data analysis module will try to automatically group and link the data during the statistics process.
- **Multi Language Support:** Datamap will support 5 languages [English, Spanish, French, Japanese and Brazilian Portuguese] with scalability.

Powerful Platform and API

RAW VIEW OF CRUD INTERFACE

PARSEC PROJECT | DataMap - Administration WELCOME, TONY | [VIEW SITE](#) / [CHANGE PASSWORD](#) / [LOG OUT](#)

[Home](#) / [Data Dictionary](#) / [Attributes](#) / [Columns](#) / [Add Attribute](#) / [Column](#)

ACCOUNTS:

- Roles [+ Add](#)
- User Profiles [+ Add](#)
- Users [+ Add](#)

AUTHENTICATION AND AUTHORIZATION

- Groups [+ Add](#)

DATA DICTIONARY

- Attachments [+ Add](#)
- Attributes | Columns [+ Add](#)**
- Datasets [+ Add](#)

Add Attribute | Column

Name:

Description:

Data Type:

Unity:
Ex: m2, cm, °C, horas, meses, anos e etc...

Default Value:
Existe um valor padrão para esse atributo? Se sim, Qual é?

Acceptable Range:
Ex: de -5°C a 35,5°C, de infravermelho até ultravioleta e etc...

Char Limit:
Ex: este campo deve ter no máximo 12 posições/caracteres

How is this calculated?
Ex: Obtido através do resultado da soma dos catetos, razão entre o seno deste ângulo e o seu cosseno e etc...

ENG

Help texts and definitions available in 5 languages

RAW VIEW OF CRUD INTERFACE

PARSEC PROJECT | DataMap - Administration WELCOME, TONY | [VIEW SITE](#) / [CHANGE PASSWORD](#) / [LOG OUT](#)

Home - Data Dictionary | Attributes | Columns ADD ATTRIBUTE | COLUMN +

ACCOUNTS

- Roles + Add
- User Profiles + Add
- Users + Add

AUTHENTICATION AND AUTHORIZATION

- Groups + Add

DATA DICTIONARY

- Attachments + Add
- Attributes | Columns + Add
- Datasets + Add

Select Attribute | Column to change

Action: Go 0 of 12 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	NAME	DATA TYPE	UNITY	IS THIS A REQUIRED ATTRIBUTE?	IS THIS A SENSITIVE DATA?	LAST UPDATE	UPDATE FREQUENCY	SOURCE OF INFORMATION
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bounce 3s	ID: Index ou Identificador	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:24 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Stravel 3s	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:22 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bounce ABS 3s	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:20 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Stravel ABS 3s	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:17 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Acel ABS 3s	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:15 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	BodyRock (mm) 3 segundos	Numérico	mm - milímetros	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:12 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bounce (mm) 3 segundos	ID: Index ou Identificador	mm - milímetros	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 4:02 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	SuspentionTravel (mm) 3 segundos	Numérico	mm - milímetros	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 3:50 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Aceleracao(g) 3 segundos	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 3:36 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Haste2Filtrado	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 3:33 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Haste1Filtrado	Numérico	G	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 3:32 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra
<input type="checkbox"/>	Linha (GTG)	Categórico	outra	✔	⊘	Aug. 20, 2020, 3:15 a.m.	Trimestral	Viagens Vagão Agosto 2020 Consolidadas - Cátedra

12 Attributes | Columns

Api Root

DATAMAP API Root

OPTIONS

GET ▾

The default basic root view for DefaultRouter

GET /api/v1/

HTTP 200 OK**Allow:** GET, HEAD, OPTIONS**Content-Type:** application/json**Vary:** Accept

```
{
  "accounts/users": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/accounts/users/",
  "userprofile": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/userprofile/",
  "datasets": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/datasets/",
  "attribute": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/attribute/",
  "accounts/auth": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/accounts/auth/token/refresh/",
  "accounts/auth/token": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/accounts/auth/token/refresh/",
  "accounts/auth/token/refresh": "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/accounts/auth/token/refresh/"
}
```

DATAMAP API Root Attribute List

Attribute List

OPTIONS

GET

GET /api/v1/attribute/

HTTP 200 OK

Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS

Content-Type: application/json

Vary: Accept

```
[
  {
    "id": 1,
    "name": "Linha (GTG)",
    "description": "Dados de identificação da via, sentido é linha.",
    "created_at": "2021-04-05T03:16:20.034191-03:00",
    "updated_at": "2021-04-05T03:16:20.034122-03:00",
    "data_type": "CATEGORICAL",
    "unit": "outra",
    "default_value": null,
    "acceptable_values": null,
    "char_limit": "10",
    "how_to_calculate": "processado pela equipe de T.I Vale através de cruzamentos de dados",
    "required": true,
    "sensitive_data": false,
    "last_update": "2020-08-20T03:15:46-03:00",
    "frequency": "Trimestral",
    "spread_sheet_tab": "DADOS_VP",
    "general_info": "",
    "ssot": 1,
    "attachment": []
  },
  {
    "id": 2,
    "name": "HasteFiltrado",
    "description": "Dados de deslocamento da Haste 1 já filtrados (descontando o valor padrão)",
    "created_at": "2021-04-05T03:32:33.977993-03:00",
    "updated_at": "2021-04-05T03:32:33.978015-03:00",
    "data_type": "NUMERICAL",
    "unit": "G",
    "default_value": null,
    "acceptable_values": null,
    "char_limit": "8",
    "how_to_calculate": "Valor padrão de rodagem do vagão carregado menos valor aferido no sensor",
    "required": true,
    "sensitive_data": false,
    "last_update": "2020-08-20T03:32:12-03:00",
    "frequency": "Trimestral",
    "spread_sheet_tab": "DADOS_VP",
    "general_info": "",
    "ssot": 1,
    "attachment": []
  },
  {
    "id": 3
```

Thank You All!